

estimated for PB, SB, SpPB, SpSB, and total spikelets (TSp). Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis ($F_{mac_1} - P_{mac}$) were significant and positive for all characters, indicating dominance of higher values.

The values for individual F_1 families, however, differed from the overall estimates for heterosis in different characters (Table 2). The F_1 means deviated conspicuously from the respective parental and midparental values, indicating nonadditive gene action for most characters.

Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction showed in characters like number of PB, SpPB, and TSp, which are related to higher grain yield potential. Most crosses exhibited positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for number of PB and SpPB; however, one Rewa cross, one upland cross, and three glaberrima crosses had negative heterobeltiosis, perhaps because of the already high number of PB and SpPB in the glaberrima parents.

Two Rewa crosses (Rewa 353-

3/IR47705-AC4 and Rewa 353-2/IR30) and three upland crosses (all but IR47705-AC5-1/IR2821143-1-1-2) manifest positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for all characters. The cross Acc. 103995/IR47705-AC4 showed negative heterobeltiosis for SB and SpSB but positive heterobeltiosis for other characters. That is desirable to increase high-density grains ($sp\ gr > 1.20$) and grain yield potential. Most poor grains or low-density grains originated from secondary branches. □

Quality attributes of seed produced on different tillers of IR50

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A bulk seed crop of IR50 was raised during 1987 dry-season (rabi). At the boot leaf stage, 20 plants were marked at random. As panicles emerged, they were numbered sequentially. At harvest, panicles were measured individually for panicle length, number of filled spikelets/tiller, seed weight/tiller, 1,000-grain weight, and germination and vigor before and after 8 d accelerated aging (see table). The vigor index is derived from length of seedling \times germination percentage.

Panicle length and seed attributes among tillers in IR50.

Tiller	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets/tiller (no.)		Seed weight/tiller (g)	1000-seed weight (g)	Before aging		After aging	
		Filled	Ill-filled			Germination (%)	Vigor index	Germination (%)	Vigor index
First	20.6	86	12	1.3	20.5	97	3780	39	820
Second	20.5	77	13	1.2	20.4	92	2910	36	730
Third	20.1	76	13	1.1	20.4	90	2650	33	620
Fourth	20.0	71	15	1.1	20.4	88	2380	30	540
Fifth	19.7	68	17	1.0	20.2	80	2100	28	480
Sixth	19.4	63	18	0.9	20.1	77	1920	26	430
Seventh	19.4	60	19	0.9	19.7	75	1820	19	290
Eighth	19.2	56	20	0.8	19.4	68	1500	17	240
Ninth	18.6	51	22	0.7	19.2	60	1230	14	160
Tenth	18.6	49	22	0.7	18.9	52	1050	11	99
Mean	19.6	66	17	0.9	19.9	78	2134	24	440
LSD (P=0.05)	1.1	4	3	0.01	0.1	7.0	192	1	41

Tillers that headed early had higher values for seed quality attributes.

The superior germination and vigor of large, early flowering tillers was evident

in the accelerated aging test. We suggest that only large, early flowering tillers/panicles be used for breeder seed increase. □

A basic plant ideotype for rice

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Plants grow within the confines of horizontal (HS) and vertical (VS) space. HS provides anchorage, VS furnishes solar energy, CO_2 , O, water, and mineral nutrients. Crop productivity depends primarily on the plants' ability to utilize HS and VS.

An efficient plant would be one which occupies the minimum HS, but the maximum VS.

Efficient use of HS by a rice cultivar implies maximum panicles per unit of HS without reduction in mean panicle yield. This requires maximum tillers per unit of HS, with no ineffective tillers, limited tiller mortality, least inter- and intraplant competition, heavy panicles, and minimum intraplant panicle yield variation. Fewer tillers per plant would minimize ineffective tillers and promote intraplant synchrony of flowering, maturity, and panicle yield. Upright growth, erect leaves, and deep roots would minimize intraplant competition.

Taller plants intercept higher amounts

of solar radiation and trap more CO_2 . Thus, taller plants promote better gas exchange between the crop and environment by creating greater humidity within the stand. Greater movement of taller culms in air currents also can improve CO_2 fixation by reducing air-layering. Longer and thicker culms can store more assimilates, up to 40% of which may be transported to the grain. Height should be the optimum to ensure lodging resistance at intended fertility levels and to provide good penetration of sunlight and air movement through the crop stand.